

Evaluation of Industrial Class Program Implementation in Vocational School

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ABSTRACT: Class industry is something form activity Which followed by participant educate selected by learning directly from teachers in the world of work, namely the business world and the industrial world in a directed manner with the aim of equipping students with appropriate attitudes and skills with the competency skills possessed by students so that they can become provisions in entering the world of work. This research aims to describe the context, input, process, and product from the industrial work practice program in the Skills Program Accounting and Finance at Nurul Hikmah II Vocational School, Bekasi City. This research is study evaluation program with use model CIPP. Approach in This research uses a qualitative approach with a description method. Informant study is Head school, head program, representative head school field curriculum as well as head of the industrial class program, the Business World and the Industrial World (DU/DI) And participant educate. Technique collection data through studies document, interview and observation. The results of the research show that the level of achievement of the class program industry on variable context program class industry in Program Skill Accountancy and The finances of the Nurul Hikmah II Vocational School Institution in Bekasi City are in the good category because in accordance with regulations And planning Which has arranged. Variable input program class industry in Accounting and Finance, Nurul Hikmah II Vocational School, Bekasi City included in the good category based on curriculum synchronization, selection of class participants industry and there is MOU with DU/DI related. Variable process program class industry in the Accounting and Finance Skills Program at Nurul Hikmah II Kota Vocational School Bekasi with the good category is implemented according to schedule and there is monitoring from head school and chairman program class industry. Variable product program class industry in the Accounting and Finance Skills Program at Nurul Hikmah II Kota Vocational School Bekasi is indicated to be very good with a competency test pass rate of 100% out of 20 participant industrial class.

KEYWORDS: Class Industry; Evaluation Program; CIPP; Accountancy And Finance Institution; vocational school

I. INTRODUCTION

Presidential Instruction Number 9 of 2016 concerning the revitalization of secondary schools Vocational: Specifically for the Ministry of Education and Culture, these are: 1) making maps development of vocational high schools; 2) refine and align vocational high school curriculum with competencies according to user needs graduate (Link and Match); 3) increasing the number and competence of educators and vocational high school education staff; 4) increase cooperation with Ministries/Institutions, Regional Governments and the Business/Industrial World; 5) improve access certification for vocational high school graduates and secondary school accreditation vocational; 6) form Group Work Development school intermediate vocational.

Bond between schools and industry very big, that is desire coaching, encouragement psychological, desire material, And utilization area industry as origin start independent training. Industrial classes are learning activities in which schools work the same as industry. Industrial classes prepare students for practical applications the next day want to used to use Work in world industry. On moment carry out activity industrial class, students have the opportunity to practice directly at the school real world atmosphere like the world of work. Through this collaboration a form will be produced as well as second industrial class program that can be profitable both parties.

Implementation class industry own level success Which Good, in plan, implement, and evaluate what is described in guide This. Level success application mark industry can is known with carry out evaluations. The assessment was carried out to determine the level of conformity between implementation program implemented by the school with guidelines.

Curriculum industry Which aims for create process learning vocational with draft Which linked and customized with need industry No will Possible materialized without involve role Teacher as educator. Process Teacher apprenticeships are an added value to the Industrial Curriculum Program and are designed for introduce condition And competence latest Which needed

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DU/DI. Recruitment is a series of processes that take place in the third stage of the process implementation class industry after school make agreement cooperation with DU/DI, after process apprenticeship Teacher. Results study show that fact show that development education Still face a number big problem unemployment Because imbalance between output education And field Work And availability field Work formal. Power Work Keep going increase every year, but no balanced with availability jobs.

Problems facing national education, especially vocational education Currently, there are many vocational school graduates who have below standard skills Which required by world business and industry. Education vocational should produce graduates in order to create a trained and ready workforce use, ready to work (ready for use).

The Industrial Class in this research is the industrial class that uses model learning and curriculum Which arranged and agreed between party school with party industry. vocational school Nurul Hikmah II City Bekasi is One of schools Which organize education class standard industry For package skill Institutional Accounting and Finance. The implementation of this class is in collaboration with DU/DI around including PT. Hexatamaprima and CV. Toga Archipelago. With implementation This class is expected to produce students who have appropriate competencies with standards required by the company/industry world.

According to the teacher at SMK Nurul Hikmah II, Bekasi City, this industrial class is supported with various excess, among them with implemented it apprenticeship in industry related. When participant educate is at in semester 3 And 4, school and industry set timetable learning in class by Teacher visitor from DU/DI related furthermore done learning to students at DU/DI offices/companies at other times alternate every month. However, at the time of implementation, several were still found One of the problems is that some teachers provide a heavy learning load the same for both industrial class and non-industrial class students, several participants educate experience difficulty in management time so that a number of task other learning becomes neglected, there is some miscommunication between the school with DU/DI and there are still limited DU/DI parties who are willing to do so For collaborate with schools in this matter.

Based on this, researchers are interested in carrying out research regarding "Evaluation of the Industrial Class Program at Nurul Hikmah II Vocational School, Bekasi City". In study This researcher use method evaluation CIPP that is: Context (includes procedure school, objective curriculum industry, curriculum), input (readiness participant teach, competence Teacher, readiness participant teach as well as equipment belonging), process (equipment, implementation of the industrial curriculum, position of teaching participants), and product (outcome). Researcher examine method, application, as well as evaluation implementation class industry on competency in financial and institutional accounting skills at SMK Nurul Hikmah II Kota Bekasi.

Basically, evaluation is providing consideration or price mark based on some criteria. Tyler explained evaluation is something process gather data For determine success in something matter And part from objective Education Which want to achieved, And If Not yet achieved searching for the cause And What Which Not yet achieved [1]. Evaluation defined vary by para expert. Hero state that evaluation is research to collect, analyze and present useful information about the evaluation object, then assessing it, and compare it with evaluation indicators and use the results to make decisions regarding the evaluation object [2]. Program evaluation is a systematic assessment of the benefits or utility something program, so that There is element judgement about mark And effectiveness of the program [3].

Definition of program evaluation is a series of activities carried out deliberately to see level program success [1]. This information is useful for decision making, among other things, to improve the program, perfect program activities continuation, stopping an activity, or disseminating an idea underlies a program or activity. The information collected must be fulfill scientific, practical, appropriate and appropriate requirements underlies every decision [4]. The purpose of holding a program evaluation is to find out achievement objective program with step know implementation Evaluation Program, Because evaluator program want to know part where from component And sub-component program Which Not yet accomplished And What why because the program evaluator wants to know which parts of the components and sub-components of the program that have not been implemented and why [1].

Determine model evaluation in activity evaluation program is matter Which very important, Because every program own characteristic Which different and every model evaluation own assumption, different approaches, terminology and logic of thinking. Effectiveness something program influenced by various factor, between other characteristics individual, environment, program objectives, facilities and infrastructure used, And procedure implementation program. Model Which First developed by Guba and Stufflebeam (1968) is oriented towards a decision (a decision oriented evaluation structured approach) . The goal is to helps administrators (managers, decision makers, principals, and Teacher) in in make decision. "Evaluation interpreted something process describe, obtain, and provide useful information for evaluate decision alternatives."

The CIPP evaluation model is considered the most comprehensive framework compared to other models. One reason is within the CIPP contains aspects of Context, Input, Process, and Product as evaluation objects. The CIPP model was developed by Daniel L. Stufflebeam in the 1960s, with objective for help repair and accountability projects school country Which financed by government Federal America Union, especially as guide For repair teaching and learning at school. The longer model CIPP the more developed and used throughout the United States and several countries other and applied in fields other. Model CIPP leave from physiosophy learning by doing- namely a continuous effort to identify and correct errors that occur in evaluation activities, for inventory and test procedures new Which needed, and for look after and combine practices which effective [5].

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Industrial Class is another form of double system education Lots in apply in School Intermediate Vocational. Finch (1979:2) characterizes it as follows "to realize work experience and to preparing young people for the transition from school to work, to learn reality work And For Ready make something choice work". Industrial Class is work experience for students Which currently prepare transition from environment School Intermediate Vocational (SMK) is an area of activity that actually controls the world of work and prepare yourself to choose the right profession. So in the program In this case, the application carried out by students is truly based on activities (work- based learning), Not in form of simulation [6].

Class industry is something form activity Where participant educate follow as well as with on duty with method direct in world work, with the aim of equipping students with actions and skills sourced from how students learn directly business or industrial world. The concept is an important component in implementing industrial practices are: 1) partnerships, 2) flexibility, 3) relevance, 4) recognition. Applying industrial grade is not just about bring participant educate to industry and give participant educate experience Work, but involved in experience Work in interaction with employee other [7].

This study aims to reveal what the implementation of the class program is industry in vocational school Nurul Hikmah II Bekasi City has in accordance with objective, principle and principle industrial class implementation in terms of context, input, process and product. The method used is an evaluation with a qualitative approach. Observations were carried out for find out the extent to which the implementation of industrial class programs is suitable. Evaluation result concluded as follows; implementation of the industrial class program at Nurul Hikmah Vocational School, It's been going on for about 1 year. And has become a pioneer for vocational school private others in sub rayon 3 Bekasi City.

Nurul Hikmah II Vocational School, Bekasi City is one of the schools in under the auspices of the Ummahatul Muslimat Pondok Gede Da'wah Foundation, school based on Islam and da'wah, without costs, prioritizing orphans poor people around environment school. With vision give service well-being to people Islam from circles race poor people through track education, social and preaching, Foundation Da'wah Ummahatul Muslimat (YDUM) Cottage Big City Bekasi Which stand since year 1992 has developing educational units; Kindergarten, TPA, SD and SMP Islam Nurul Wisdom II Bekasi City. See many graduates of JUNIOR HIGH SCHOOL/ Tsanawiyah in around Village Ricefield especially the poor have not been able to continue to the next level of school, so as organizer free social-based education and da'wah Which

METHOD

The concept of the research method used is a qualitative method with a descriptive approach based on evaluation research using an approach qualitative and the CIPP (Context, Input, Process, Product) model developed by Stufflebeam. Model This chosen Because is model evaluation Which very appropriate For evaluate the effectiveness of implementing a program, including evaluation of use instructional Media. The technique in this research is descriptive because this research analyze something circumstances, use analysis descriptive qualitative started from analysis various data Which collected from something study Then move to direction formation of conclusions. Therefore, this descriptive analysis starts from classification data. In the descriptive research method with a qualitative approach, the method the analysis is a qualitative analysis method. Taking into account that this research seeks to describe social phenomena that occur in the learning environment in Vocational High School (SMK) Nurul Hikmah II Bekasi City.

Objective from evaluation Which done is for analyze and evaluate implementation class industry in vocational school Nurul Wisdom II City Bekasi seen from facet context, input, process and product. This research also aims to socialize the program class industry to various party including public to use give chance Which as widely as possible to all students to obtain applied education in accordance with need market. Help government in speed up process improving the quality of education through improving learning services in the world education. The subjects in this research are sources who can provide information in an informative manner objective, actual and natural. Informant study is Head school, head program as well as head of the industrial class program, deputy principal for curriculum, DU/DI and learners.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Result

The results of research regarding: First, Implementation context class industry

a. Base law; School Intermediate vocational (Vocational School) is level education formal skills that provide special skills in preparing graduates ready to work. Based on Government Regulation Number 29 of the year 1990 concerning secondary education, objectives of secondary education article 3 paragraph that is Education intermediate vocational prioritize setup participant educate for enter field Work as well as develop attitude professional. In Law No. 20 of 2003 concerning the National Education System Article 15 Also explain that objective School Intermediate Vocational (Vocational School) is secondary education that prepares students primarily for work on field certain. Thereby Also Instructions President Number 9 year 2016 about Revitalization School Intermediate Vocational And Regulation Minister Education And Culture Republic Indonesia Number 22 Year 2016 about Standard Process Education Base And Intermediate as well as Regulation Minister Industry Number 3 Year 2017 about Guidelines And Development School Competency-Based Vocational Intermediate that Links and Machs with

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Industry. As school Which own objective For Ready enter field work means School Intermediate Vocational (Vocational School) must own program skill so that relevance with the Business World and World Industry (DU/DI). But For adapt with World Business And World Industry (DU/DI) very difficult, Wrong the only one because gap Which happen between industry increase, Wrong One effort Which done school And party industry is with form class Industry. It was formed class Industry This expected will produce participant educate Which own competence Which in accordance with standard Which required by industry Which cooperate with school.

b. Background behind; Industrial class is also one of the implementation patterns education Which held in School Intermediate Vocational (Vocational School) Which combine between system education school And system Which There is in Industry relevant to schools and industry. the gap is a gap technology, school curriculum that is not yet in line with industry needs and teaching staff who have not been able to keep up with what is happening in the industrial world. Matter This cause readiness graduate of school intermediate vocational become not enough. Gaps Which happen between institution education And world industry Therefore, cooperation is needed that can reduce this gap, so that education Which held in school can follow developments with the times and produce graduates who suit needs market. With exists cooperation industry This process education Which There is at school customized with need industry. Matter This expected absorption graduates in the industrial world and are aimed at achieving competency mastery participant educate in accordance with the development of science knowledge and technology. From the results of the interview it was found that the implementation of the industrial class program At Nurul Hikmah Vocational School it has been running for approximately 1 year. And it has become a pioneer for other private vocational schools in sub-rayon 3 Kota Bekasi. As for class industry the cooperate with IDUKA (Industry And World Work) PT. HEKSATAMA PRIMA, KAJ (Consultant Service Accountant) SUNARMIN and CV. GRIYA AN-NUR.

c. Objective from implementation class industry; Results Which expected from implementation class industry in vocational school is: a) Availability graduate of Which superior in accordance with demands And hope world business, industrial world and working world, b) Increasing the quality of learning management in vocational schools in accordance with demands standards of the business world, industrial world and the world of work, c) Increasing Skills, abilities and graduate professionalism vocational school; d) Increasing absorption And Power competitive graduate of vocational school in world business, world industry and the world of work; e) Availability model learning Which designed together world business, world industry and the world of work to fulfill the special competencies of vocational school graduates Which requested by the world business, industrial world and working world

Second, Implementation input class industry

a. Participant educate participants class industry; Participant educate Which can follow class industry in vocational school Nurul Wisdom II are selected students who have passed the selection held by school with agreement with DU/DI. The selection process is carried out to class XI students at the beginning of the even semester. In the selection process participant educate given series instruments test in a way written And oral For resolved with carefully. So that be chosen 20 participant educate best For furthermore follow class program industry which was announced by school.

The learning targets during the industrial class are as follows table following:

Table 2. Targets learning of class industry

No.	Aspect Ability	DU/DI
1	Learning Ethics Profession	PT. HEKSATAMA PRIME
2	Learning Content Creator (Tiktok)	PT. HEKSATAMA PRIME
3	Training tax And charging SPT tax personal	KAJ SUNARMIN
4	Calculation And charging as well as reporting PPHbody for entrepreneurs MSMEs	KAJ SUNARMIN
5	Grow soul entrepreneurship	CV. GRIYA AN-NUR

b. Means and infrastructure supporter; Supporting facilities and infrastructure in the implementation of this industrial class, The school has provided a computer lab room containing 24 units computer and has installed supporting devices and applications. Then After several meetings, students will take part in direct practice at PT. Hexatama Prime according to that schedule has been determined.

c. Curriculum of class Industry; On planning curriculum class Industry done with method synchronization between curriculum 2013 vocational school Nurul Wisdom II City Bekasi with IDUKA who communicates with schools regarding the curriculum which is used by schools and then industry adapts school curriculum with industry needs. Curriculum planning in class industry done with method synchronization curriculum national And curriculum industry, matter This showing that curriculum class industry formed based on the needs of students, especially in oriented vocational schools on output that is ready to enter the world Work.

Third, Implementation process class industry

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a. Implementation Learning; Based on results observation, implementation learning on class 75 industry in accordance with the established curriculum planning. In the implementation of learning, method Which used is Implementation Learning Implementation learning on class industry in accordance with planning curriculum which has been set. In implementing learning, the methods used are worksheets/assignments, classroom learning and practice. For vocational school practice have more lesson hours than delivering material in class, p This aims to prepare independent vocational school graduates to enter world Work and meet needs industry in energy requirements Work. Learning on class industry Already Good Because learning more emphasize on method learning practice And Output on class industry Already prepared to enter the industrial world, especially in collaborating industries with that industrial class. In terms of preparing the output, students has equipped material Which relate with industry the like Professional Ethics Learning and Content Creator Learning (Tiktok) by PT. HEKSATAMA PRIMA, Training tax And charging SPT tax personal And Calculation And charging as well as reporting PPH body For businessman MSMEs by KAJ SUNARMIN and Fostering an entrepreneurial spirit by CV. GRIYA AN- NUR. This is an added value for the graduating class industry to have opportunity Work on industry who collaborates with class industry the. Then in its implementation, Nurul Hikmah II Vocational School, Bekasi City has prepare activity agendas ranging from socialization to implementation of learning And internship activities on industrial class.

b. Monitoring; In implementing industrial class programs, students of course monitored by the Head of the Institute's Accounting and Finance Study Program, in matter This is Mother Ida Erawati S.E., along with all committee Which has formed school. Matter This Chairman Program Studies in monitoring aim For monitor How participant educate capable follow activity class industry, know ability participant educate in control competence field skill Which has planned. Following Also with DU/DI Which has Work The same carry out regular monitoring and reporting to the Head of the Study Program Accountancy and Finance Institution.

Fourth, Implementation product class industry; Product evaluation is an assessment carried out in order to see achievement/success something program in reach objective Which has previously determined. The objectives or expected results of implementation class industries in vocational schools are: a) Availability graduate of Which superior in accordance with demands And hope world business, industrial world and working world; b) Increasing quality management learning in vocational school in accordance with demands standards of the business world, industrial world and working world; c) Increasing Skills, abilities and graduate professionalism vocational school; d) Increasing the absorption and competitiveness of vocational school graduates in the business world, world industry and the world of work; e) Availability of learning models designed with the business world, the world industry And world Work For fulfillment competence special graduate of vocational school Which requested by the world business, industry and the world of work Based on the above objectives, the industrial class program implemented by participant educate participant class industry vocational school Nurul Wisdom II City Bekasi already accomplished with Good in accordance with objective the. On objective points First, results from Program class industry This besides give experience to world Work, but it can also be used as experience in the long term, namely on when students become graduates, they can give it to students others in the form of insight, knowledge and experience regarding various kinds abilities and work as well as how to deal with everything that happens during the process class industry taking place in agency or company. Matter This proven with There are several industrial class participants who have received more facilities from agency or company form certificate, Eat Afternoon even Money incentive from companies that have collaborated. On points final, vocational school Nurul Wisdom II City Bekasi has own guide And experience application model learning Which has designed together world business, world industry And world Work For furthermore can developed according to current needs.

Fifth, Obstacle And challenge in implementation class industry; As for in his journey, based on results interview that application class industry in vocational school Nurul Wisdom II City Bekasi experience a number of obstacle among them is: a) Some teachers give the same learning load to both students class industrial and non-industrial class; b) Some students experience difficulties in time management so a number of other learning tasks become neglected; c) There is a number of miscommunication between the school with parties DU/DI; d) Still limited party DU/DI Which please For do cooperation with school in this case.

DISCUSSION

Based on the results of the research described above, the results research can put forward several findings results evaluation of industrial class programs on Accounting and Finance skills competencies Institution at Nurul Vocational School Wisdom II of Bekasi City, namely:

First, Stages Context (Context); In the Context component which includes legal basis, background, the vision and mission of the school, the objectives of holding the program, and the cooperation text, and the competency profile of the Institution's Accounting and Finance expertise is very good result and in accordance with guidelines Which has determined Which grounded Minister of Education and Culture Regulation Number 60 year 2014 about Structure Curriculum SMK/MAK, Decree of the Minister of Education and Culture Number 323/U/1997 concerning the Implementation of Education Dual System and Law Number 20/2003 concerning the National Education System as well Kep. Minister of Manpower Number 285/MEN/1991 concerning Implementation of National Apprenticeships, also with curriculum school Which has been synchronized with DU/DI

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related. Although Still There is lack in suitability program with students' needs in meeting DU/DI needs. For this shortcoming so should done cooperation Which better between school with agency related for more increase Skills in accordance with competence his expertise. Which where component context can help plan decisions, determining the needs to be achieved by the program, formulating program objectives (Yusuf, 2000). Likewise with the number of DU/DI that still exist limited new only 3 DU/DI just that is PT. HEKSATAMA PRIMA, Consultant Service Accountant (KJA) SUNARMIN, CV. GRIYA AN-NUR. For That to the front should stage cooperation with DU/DI Which more Lots To use support success Which even better on the program this industrial class.

Second, Input Components (Input); Component input/input help arrange decision, determine existing resources, what alternatives were taken, what plans and strategies for reach objective, And How procedure Work For achieve it [8]. On study This school has strive preparation/strategy implementation program Which covers committee, target, agreement Work And stage book guide, procedure placement participant education and design curriculum and placement of students which includes socialization and provision, scheduling program Work, means And infrastructure, management budget And source human resources, so that in implementation the results are very good. But deep this input component still has shortcomings, namely: aspects of socialization and provision Which where the time too sudden so that person old participant No everything Which present, For to the front will repaired so that participant And person Parents will prepare themselves better, especially in terms of time for their children's education they.

Third, Stages Process (Process); Component process is implementation strategy and use facilities/material capital in real field activities [9]. On This research process stage has been carried out very well. How long the implementation of industrial classes has been determined jointly between the school and DU/DI. Place implementation class industry and type work Which will given already relevant with competence. Done Supervision Good by party school nor party DU/DI For monitor presence participant educate, as well as made journal activity daily during class industry so that its implementation walks with fluent.

However, deficiencies are still found in this component participant that is Still lack of guidance, monitoring and suggestions/solutions Which given by the supervisor/supervisor. Also with the condition of facilities and infrastructure In the form of computers owned by the school, there are sufficient numbers participant educate participant class industry, However with application Which Still said need there are the latest updates, especially regarding the operating system use windows 7 And office 2013, should done renewal form operating windows 10 and office systems 2019.

Fourth, Stages Products (Product); According to Munir, evaluating these results is the final stage, namely evaluation regarding the success or failure of participants in achieving the set goals [10]. Nana Sudjana believes that product evaluation is the result achieved in maintenance the program [11]. Activity evaluation This aims to help with subsequent decisions. Questions that must be answered is results What Which has achieved And What Which done after program walk [12]. In this research, the product components were implemented with good results Very good. In an effort to find out how successful the implementation was program This Can seen from enhancement Skills, enhancement understanding areas task, interpretation superiority and weakness program Which used as well as proven with exists certificate skill Which participant educate get it from DU/DI related. However, as time goes by, most students work in fields that do not match the work experience that students have get. Therefore, the school should do something about this deficiency Collaboration with related DU/DI to place students in the industrial world DU/DI that for several time.

Fifth, Obstacle And challenge in implementation class industry; As for in his journey, results interview that application class The industry at Nurul Hikmah II Vocational School, Bekasi City, is experiencing several obstacles among them is: a) Some teachers give the same learning load to both students industrial class and non-industrial class, thus creating challenges How communication And socialization with Good to all over element school For increase understanding And equality perception sake smoothness implementation of industrial class programs.; b) Some students experience difficulties in time management so a number of task learning other become abandoned, so that For The challenge is to provide guidance and communication to participants educate as well as provide more assistance intensive.; c) There were several miscommunications between the school and DU/DI, so the challenge is how to collaborate between schools and parties DU/DI runs well, communicates well with meeting more intensive; d) Still limited party DU/DI Which please For do cooperation with school. And to challenge this, the school makes various efforts establishing networks and relationships with DU/DI in accordance with the program skill Institutional accounting and finance.

CONCLUSIONS AND SUGGESTIONS

The evaluation of industrial class program implementation in vocational school are: Stages Context (Context); In the Context component which includes legal basis, background, the vision and mission of the school, the objectives of holding the program, and the cooperation text, and the competency profile of the Institution's Accounting and Finance expertise is very good Good And in accordance with guidelines Which has determined Which grounded Minister of Education and Culture Regulation Number 60 year 2014 about Structure Curriculum SMK/MAK, Decree of the Minister of Education and Culture Number 323/U/1997 concerning the Implementation of Education Dual System and Law Number 20/2003 concerning the National

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Education System as well Kep. Minister of Manpower Number 285/MEN/1991 concerning Implementation of National Apprenticeships, Also with curriculum school Which has been synchronized with DU/DI related.; b. Input Components (Input); On component input, school has strive preparation/strategy implementation program Which covers committee, target, agreement Work And stage book guide, procedure placement participant educate And design curriculum And placement participant educate Which covers socialization And provision, scheduling program Work, means And infrastructure, management budget And source Power human, so in implementation the result Very good; c. Stages Process (Process); In this research, the process stages have been carried out very well. The duration of industrial class implementation has been determined jointly between the school and DU/DI. Place of industrial class implementation and type of work to be given is relevant to competence. Good supervision is carried out by the school as well as DU/DI to monitor student attendance, and create daily activity journal during industrial class so that implementation runs smoothly fluent.; d. Stages Products (Product); In this research, the product components were implemented with good results Very good. In an effort to find out how successful the implementation was program This Can seen from enhancement Skills, enhancement understanding areas task, interpretation superiority And weakness program Which used as well as proven with exists certificate skill Which participant educate get it from DU/DI related; e. Obstacle And challenge in implementation class industry; a. Some teachers give the same learning load to both students class industry nor Which non class industry, so that give rise to challenge How communication And socialization with Good to all over element school For increase understanding And equality perception sake smoothness implementation of industrial class programs.; b. Some students experience difficulties in time management so a number of task learning other become abandoned, so that For The challenge is to provide guidance and communication to participants educate as well as provide more assistance intensive.; c. There were several miscommunications between the school and DU/DI, so the challenge is how to collaborate between schools and parties DU/DI runs well, communicates well with meeting more intensive; d. There are still limited DU/DI parties who are willing to collaborate with school. And to challenge this, the school makes various efforts establishing networks and relationships with DU/DI in accordance with the program skill Institutional accounting and finance.

Based on results findings study Which has concluded in on, so following a number of suggestions or that recommendation can be taken into consideration: 1. To schools, especially foundations, to support school programs with provide more adequate facilities for the entire school program walk especially well industrial class program; 2. To head school so that more monitoring planning And implementation industrial class programs including holding collaborations with more DU/DI Lots To use support success Which more Good Again on this program of class industry. Including the condition of facilities and infrastructure in the form of computers Which owned by school amount Enough in accordance amount participant educate participant class industry, but with applications that are still said to need updating Which latest especially to operating system Which Still use windows 7 And office 2013, should done renewal form operating system windows 10 and office 2019; 3. To the curriculum section to make it more adaptable program according to needs students in meeting DU/DI needs. By collaborating between schools and related agencies to further improve Skills according to their competency skills; 4. To part head program And chairman safety pin program class industry so that compile planning program Which more ripe especially scheduling guidance and monitoring for industrial class participants. And it's best to do it Collaboration with related DU/DI to place students in the industrial world DU/DI that for several time.

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